

TRANSLATION PROCESSES IN ARAB COUNTRIES**Kudratov Azamat Asrorovich,***Basic doctoral student of the Department of**Translation Studies and International Journalism,**Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.**Phone: (71) 2430841; GSM: 97 156 90 03; email: Azeem7997@gmail.com*

Abstract Despite the fact that the field of translation is a rather laborious job, the demand and supply for this direction is increasing. The time itself demands this. Translation is a communicative tool that serves the spiritual needs of another people and creates an opportunity for artistic enjoyment of a work created in one language. Currently, due to the rapid development of this field in the Arabs, various research scientists have been deeply organized by researchers to understand how this process developed in history and during the Caliphate and the subsequent periods. . In addition, the Arabs used the philosophical writings of the Greeks to master theology, homiletics, and mainly apologetics by translating them into Arabic. In this article, our main task was to study the processes and stages of translation in Arabic, and scientific results were obtained.

Keywords: History of translation, oral translation, Hurun Hubbin, Umaviys, Bayt al-Hikma, Bayt Al-Hikma, Aristotle and Plato, Nahda.

They assumed that people have known oral translation since the beginning of languages, and people needed translators to communicate in their commercial relations, travel, and political conversations [1, 30].

Since translation relies mainly on the translation of spoken words, scholars or historians could not document the stages of this type of translation and its development over the centuries, especially since translation techniques that rely on

techniques and audio equipment were not known before the mid-twentieth century[2, 21].

According to the sources, the oldest evidence of the use of translation by man can be seen in the inscriptions of the Pharaoh, “حب أم حور” in the statue of Hurun or Hubbin. (Hurun or Hubbin was the last pharaoh of the eighteenth Egyptian family in the history of ancient Egypt) He was engaged in translation before becoming a pharaoh, and this was in the fourteenth century [2, 21].

In the history of Islam, the duty of a translator is mentioned in the blessed Sunnah, and our Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) entrusted the translation to his great companion Zayd bin Thabit, so he learned several languages for it.

Kharija ibn Zayd ibn Thabit, may God bless him and grant him peace, narrates: "The Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace, ordered him to study the book of the Jews until I write his books (the book of the Jews) to the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace, and if he writes to him until I read his books[3, 12].

The period when the Arabs were actively engaged in translation began with the period of Muawiyah (661-680), the first caliph of the Umayyad dynasty. Before that, there was a need for translation when the religion of Islam came into existence and spread from the Arabian Peninsula to the outskirts. One of the recognized points is that the demand for oral translation arose when our Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) and the Muslim community migrated from Makkah to Yathrib (Madinah). The reason is that at that time there were two Arabs: Hazraj and Aws and three Jewish tribes: Bani Nazir, Bani Qaynuqa and Bani Qurayza. Although Arabic and Jewish languages belong to the same language family - Semitic, translation has always been necessary for mutual understanding [4, 320].

According to historical facts, Muslims under the leadership of the Prophet signed a treaty between each tribe. It should be noted that political scientists

recognize that the requirements of this agreement concluded in the 7th century are different from modern confederation agreements both in form and content [5]. Due to the disagreements that started to arise with the Jews in some places on the issue of rulings, some of the Companions learned the Jewish language and worked on translation with the instructions of the Prophet, peace be upon him. For this reason, it can be concluded that translation processes fundamentally started in the Arabs in the 7th century.

During the Umayyad period, Arabic writing was improved, and science and art developed, in particular, Muslims translated works related to medicine, natural science, and philosophy from Greece.

Reliable information about the development of Arabic writing as a basis for creative literature has been preserved since the reign of Muawiya (661-680), who showed a great interest in tribal traditions and the legendary history of Arabia, and under whom the Library of Alexandria translations of the works were also created [6, 10].

Already there were translations of works on catastrophes and medicine, astrology and alchemy, philosophy and logic. During the Abbasid dynasty, in 750-850, Bayt Al-Hikma (House of Wisdom) was established in Baghdad under Caliph Harun Al-Rashid, who specialized only in Arabic translations. In today's language, the Academy has started work. During the period of his son Ma'mun (813-833), the activity of academic research carried out a lot of work in the development of exact sciences, and translators and scientists had a great role in this process. The activity of translators acquired a scientific character at that time [7, 83].

After al-Mu'tasim came to power (833-842), the Abbasid dynasty moved the capital to the newly built city of Samarra. The activity of "Baytul-Hikma" that remained in Baghdad will decrease significantly due to some political events that took place in the country. Only a large library called "Khizanat al-Ma'mun" ("Treasure of Ma'mun"), which was used by many scholars between the 9th and

10th centuries remains as a center for the dissemination of knowledge. However, soon after, the references to him also disappeared [8, 269].

In addition to the above, there were three other libraries in Baghdad (9th century). One of them belonged to the Arab poet and singer Ali ibn Yahya (who died in 888) and was located in a palace in the suburbs near Baghdad, where scholars lived, did scientific work, and could get all the necessary information from library sources[9, 269]. Ali ibn Yahya was the founder of the second library. He gave some of his books, copies of which were taken, to his foundation. The library was visited by ordinary people and scholars from the cities of Basra and Kufa.

In the Middle Ages, there were specific types of libraries (palace, private, educational and scientific institutions) that differed from others. It should be noted that these libraries are considered Islamic properties. They did not belong to one person but were the "eternal possession" of the Islamic community. The uniqueness of these libraries is that all Arab caliphs tried to enrich them.

The sons of Musa ibn Shakir: Muhammad, Ahmed and Hasan established a very rich library containing books on ancient sciences and actively collected many books for its fund. Thus, collections of Arabic works from the central regions of the caliphate (Iraq, Syria, Hejaz, Egypt) found their way to other regions of the caliphate and began to spread in countries such as Iran, Central Asia, Transcaucasia, North Africa, and Spain.

By the end of the 9th century, the aforementioned libraries disappeared and were replaced by vaqf libraries¹. The owners of the library turned their private libraries into the property of the foundation in the hope of reward. We should note

¹ **ВАҚФ** (араб.) — [МУСУЛМОН](#) мамлакатларида [ДАВЛАТ](#) ёки айрим шахслар томонидан диний эҳтиёж ёки хайрия ишлари учун ажратилган мол-мулк. [Вақфнома](#) орқали расмийлаштирилади. Ер-сув, уй-жой, мактаб, масжид, [шифоҳона](#), кутубхона ва бошқалар вақф мулки бўлиши мумкин. Ўз мулкани Вақфга топширган [шахс](#) мазкур мулкка нисбатан эгалик ҳуқуқини йўқотади. Лекин унинг ўзи ёки [оила](#) аъзолари ёхуд учинчи бир шахс Вақф мулкидан вақфномада қайд этилган мақсадларда фойдаланилаётганлигини аниқлаш учун Вақф мулкани [бошқариш](#) ҳуқуқини сақлаб қолиши мумкин. Ўз мулкани Вақф мулки сифатида топширган шахснинг фарзандлари ёки бошқа авлодлари мазкур Вақф мулкидан келадиган даромадлардан [нафақа](#) олиб туриши мумкин. Вақф мулкани [шариат](#) қонуни бўйича [давлат бошлиғи](#) ёки [қози](#) назорат қилади. Бу [тартиб](#) Шарқнинг баъзи мамлакатларида ҳозир ҳам амалда. Ад.: Бурхониддин Маргинаний, Хидая, Т., 1994; Мухтасар (Шариат қрунларига қисқача [шарҳ](#)), Т., 1994.

that in the second half of the 9th century, new books, translations, collections of commentaries on the Qur'an, chronicles, Arabic geographical and medical writings, and fiction appeared in the Arab world [9, 217]. Philosophical translation activity has developed in its own way. Arabs translated the works of Aristotle and Plato. In addition, we can recall the works of early Muslim rationalist philosophers - Mu'tazilites, preserved in Hebrew-Arabic manuscripts. Among them, al-Kindi (died 870), the first Arab philosopher who tried to combine the Greek and Muslim philosophy of life, and al-Farabi (died 950), who was considered the second teacher after Aristotle and authored several philosophical and socio-ethical treatises. In the Middle Ages, the works of the Spanish school of Toledo philosophers Ibn Baj, Ibn Tufail and Ibn Rushd were popular in Europe [9, 247].

The Arabs used Greek philosophical writings to master theology, homiletics, and mainly apologetics. They also cited examples from the treatises of ancient philosophers as arguments, thus engaging in polemics with paganism, Zoroastrianism, and later Islam.

From the beginning of the 11th century, there was stagnation in the development of literature and science in the Arabs, which in turn led to a decrease in the volume of translations. Among them are the translations of the historical work "Oroziya" from Latin in Spain and Beruni from Sanskrit in Ghazna.

After the Mongols conquered Iraq in the period from the 13th to the 15th century, the centers of Arab culture moved to Syria and Egypt and appeared in the Maghreb countries, Iraq and Spain [9, 218]. Between the 15th and 19th centuries, Arab scientific centers disappeared due to the gradual conquest of Andalusia by Catholics in Europe and its fall in 1492. Meanwhile, as the Arab civilization declined, the Ottoman Empire began to flourish in the Islamic world (1516-1923). The Ottomans captured Constantinople in 1453, completely conquered Byzantium, and began to strengthen their position in the Balkans and Central Europe. During the reign of Mehmed II (1432-1481) and Suleiman the Magnificent (1494-1566) from the 11th century to the end of the 16th century, the Ottoman Empire reached

the peak of its prosperity. In that period, new scientific centers such as Bursa, Edirne, Istanbul, Amasya, and Sarajevo were created. Scientists from Egypt, Syria, Iran, Mavarounnahr, and neighboring European countries were invited there.

In the period from the end of the 17th century to the 19th century, the Ottoman Empire began to strengthen its position in front of the power of the Austrian and Russian empires. Thus, from the end of the 11th century to the middle of the 19th century, translations from Arabic into Latin and other European languages began to appear in Europe, but the Arabs themselves stopped paying attention to translation as before. Therefore, we cannot say that the Arabs were very active in the art of translation during this period. In our opinion, there are no sources from that period that describe the issue of translation criticism or a scientific discussion on similar issues.

In the second half of the 19th century, the Arab world experienced a period of "Nahda" ("Renaissance") in literature, politics, culture, and religion. All this was connected with the historical events in Egypt, that is, the weakening of the Ottoman Empire and the establishment of huge French colonies in the Middle East by Napoleon in a short period of time (1798-1801). After Muhammad Ali² came to power in Egypt, special emissaries were sent to France during his time to study French culture and the French language. Among them was Rifaa al-Takhtawi, who later established a translation school in Egypt in 1835[10, 267].

During the Ottoman Empire, the position of the Arabic language in terms of translation weakened. Another important reason for this was the increase in the number of translations from European languages. Then, in the second half of the 19th century, the translation of French, German, and English novels gave a new impetus to the development of the Arabic translation process. At the beginning of the 20th and 21st centuries, the importance of Arabic literature weakened again. As a result of crises and wars, economic, political and financial problems have come

² Мухаммад Али (1769-1848), Миср волийси (1805-1848) (Усмонли Турк империяси вассали).

to the fore due to changes in priorities. Due to the events taking place in Arab countries, the translation business has been neglected.

It is known that translation is closely related to the development of the science of linguistics. In linguistics, the general language situation, language development and its main trends and factors are discussed in detail. Any language works and develops in an integral relationship with society. On the one hand, language appears as a historical necessity and meets certain requirements that society has set or will set for it. On the other hand, the language reflects the state of society and creates a basis for its active development. This is where the two-way relationship between language and society is revealed. It would be no mistake to say that this is where the attitude towards translation is formed. Translation from foreign languages into the native language is primarily based on the needs and level of the society.

For this reason, it is appropriate to study the general state of society and its socioeconomic development as criteria for language development. If the society is backward, the language of the people cannot develop. Also, on the contrary, there cannot be an underdeveloped language in developed societies. This development directly affects the scope and content of translation [11, 176].

A language developed in this way is a means of communication between people in a society characterized by a relatively high level of development of production, technology, culture, and social and political life achieved by a man during a certain historical period. Translation and translation studies will also develop accordingly.

The lexicon of a language is a factor that more accurately reflects the development of a language. However, at the same time, things and situations that are less needed in society fall out of the vocabulary of the language, that is, the lexical layer. Because those words have no importance in modern life. The increase in the richness of the language vocabulary is a simultaneous process with the qualitative enrichment of the entire lexicon [11, 176]. This is determined by the

increase of words that allow us to more clearly express the intellectual-emotional side of the life of a society. A skilled translator should follow the lexical changes in the language and try to use common and understandable expressions when using words in translation.

The development of vocabulary is often observed at a steady pace during periods of sharp social awakening in society. For example, in the times of national renaissance and self-realization of the nation, it is noticeable that the vocabulary of the artistic language is richer than in other periods. Also, this development will not fail to have an impact on translation studies.

Another factor of translation studies and language development is stylistic differentiation, that is, stylistic diversity occurs. If we observe the style of everyday speech, folklore and fairy tales in less developed languages that are not expressed in writing, then in well-developed literary languages, in addition to the above, we will inevitably see artistic, journalistic, scientific, official-business and other style systems. It can be seen from this opinion that it is necessary to pay attention to these factors in the development of translators.

Likewise, we can say that the level of language development is closely related to the socio-communicative level of language activity and, in turn, determines the level of development of the nation and the social-ethnic unity of the people. Society cannot be said to be passive in language development. On the contrary, a community or a community within a community acts as a leader in language development. Social relationships have a significant impact on language development. Especially in the development of artistic language norms, society has an active influence on language development [11, 176].

CONCLUSION

During the caliphate, works related to calamity and medicine, astrology and alchemy, philosophy and logic were translated more. The Arabs used Greek philosophical writings to master theology, homiletics, and mainly apologetics. Until the 20th century, the word "translation" was used only for the translation of

historical, philosophical, literary and artistic works. The term "tilmoch" is used in Turkic peoples, "delimitation" in German, and "interpreter" in English and French. The ideas expressed in the theory of translation have gained a general meaning.

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